

**The Rise of Opaque Products as an Efficient Revenue Management Technique in the
Travel Industry**

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Abstract

This paper discusses and reviews in detail about opaque products which is also known as probabilistic goods, right from its inception and beginnings in early 2000's. Opaque products are virtual goods and can be considered as a relatively new revenue management technique that has aided mainly the travel industry, specifically the airlines and hotels to increase their revenues and profits by intentionally withholding certain key information for some of the products to the customers. For Example, in airline industry the information may be product attributes like carrier, transfers, departure time etc. These products primarily trades consumption value for price savings with the buyers. Several models of opaque products which segment the market, thereby enhancing price discrimination and providing revenue enhancement, specifically in the airline industry have been described in this paper. A specific type of opaque product known as variable opaque product has also been described. Such variable opaque products allow the customer to pick and choose the attributes thereby varying the opaqueness. Thus, they have been found extremely advantageous and provide financial benefits to the airlines while providing welfare to the customers. The advantages of opaque selling models both to the customer as well as the airlines under certain types of environment has also been discussed along with its extensive applications in seat inventory control and inter-temporal pricing. Finally, the paper comes up with a few useful propositions that can be either tested empirically or modelled appropriately along with probable future work that should provide a vivid reader with the necessary spark that would aid him or her to contribute to further useful work in this area.

Keywords: Opaque Products, Travel Industry, Airlines, Probabilistic Goods, Variable Opaque Products.

1 Introduction

Opaque selling which is also known as probabilistic selling is a unique type of offering where the seller masks the service or product identity until the buyer makes the payment (Fay and Xie, 2008). Companies in the USA like Priceline, Hot wire, Cheap Tickets etc. have introduced this concept to sell hotel rooms, airline travel tickets and car rentals. In the USA and developed economies this practice has gained a lot of popularity since its inception in late nineties to early 2000's. In Asian countries like India, too the practice is gaining popularity specifically among airlines, the best examples being make my trip, Yatra etc. which act as the intermediaries selling the opaque service or product. This is because it mainly discriminates the price between heterogeneous consumers with variety of preferences thereby reducing mismatches between capacity and demand uncertainty as well as softening the price competition (Jerath et al. 2010, Shapiro and Shi 2008). It is equally advantageous to the consumers as they also get the products at a price which is quite lower than they would have gotten otherwise. For example, if a consumer provides the price for a hotel room, its type, the date on which he is going to rent the room, the opaque selling intermediary runs the auction with its designated hotels that fit the requirements of the customer. The transaction is completed successfully by the intermediary if the bid is below the consumer's named price. Finally, the intermediary informs the customer about hotel's location to which they are assigned. Sometimes the reverse auction also happens, like the intermediary posts the price to the customer while hiding the provider's details. Hence, the opaque selling by intermediaries can be applied to any sort of industry where upstream providers or sellers can be horizontally differentiated. Though, one big disadvantage is that the customers should trade-off between the certain price that they pay and the uncertain value the service or product offers. Further they also need to depend on other's experiences for their buying decisions. In the next section we explore and review the literature from revenue management and operations perspective, followed by section 3 that describes diverse types of opaque products, specifically variable opaque products along with the industries where these products can be applied. We conclude the paper through certain useful propositions that can aid this phenomenon in successful implementation.

2 Literature Review

In this paper, we have tried to contribute to revenue management research to a relatively new phenomenon known as probabilistic goods or opaque products. Inter-temporal sales literature

and work started with Coase (1972) conjecture which postulates that customers will anticipate a decrease of price of a monopolist and hence delay purchases. Some papers (DeGraba, 1995) contrasted with this conjecture and suggested that on a limited availability of product, customer's waiting may not be an advantage for lowering of price as this may not happen. Though there are less papers regarding opaque selling and its mechanisms, Jiang (2007) has considered opaque selling for flights which were owned by same firm but were scheduled on various times in the day. Shapiro and Shi (2008) reiterate that opaque selling enables the upstream sellers to differentiate the price among customers who respond to a product or service with higher degrees of sensitivity. Further Deneckre and Moore (1996) introduced the concept of selling inferior as well as damaged goods, to bring in price discrimination among customers who may have different values of reservation. Thus, even though the opaque product may be considered as inferior goods, by nature at-least two visible and transparent goods will be sold with each opaque. Results from Rey and Stiglitz (1995) implies that higher profits can be achieved for oligopolists through separation than through vertical integration and when price is set by downstream sellers and retailers. Thus, opaque intermediary's selling tactics allows wholesalers and producers to segment a given market which aids in charging greater price to loyals than non-loyals. Fay (2005) states that though the intermediary plays they key role in selling of opaque products, they are not the active decision holders. Thus, the actual decisions lay in the hands of customer or the upstream sellers. Studies by Huang and Chen have tried to explore the role of bounded rationality among customers that affects the product or a service fill rate i.e. case of likelihood of a stock-out as well as the pre-order price. Studies also indicate that, with the increasing use of e-commerce, opaque market could be created in different online channels by hiding certain key information from the consumers. Though Talluri and Van Ryzen (2004) have assumed that consumer demand is not affected by competition and product availability, a very important aspect which is the customers waiting strategically for lowering of prices has not been studied in detail.

In the final part of this section, we illustrate the taxonomy of major research studies as shown in Table 1. These are classified based on the modelling framework. Main differentiation dimension is competition among providers where papers by Jiang and Fay/Xie provide their models based on monopolistic settings whereas Shapiro and Shi base their model on selling opaque products using intermediaries. Demand uncertainties are considered by Jerath and Fay/Xie. One of the other dimensions in consideration was the model being based on single

period also known as static model vs dynamic model which was based on multi-period. Only Jerath's model was based on multi period where two firms involved in competition initially sell their transparent tickets at face prices and then sell the left-over tickets as opaque products through an intermediary. Finally, in the presence of competition, Shapiro and Shi as well as Fay consider the presence of Strategic Intermediary i.e. whether decisions are made by them or whether the decisions are made by consumers and upstream sellers. In this paper the models are not described in detail and vivid readers are requested to go through Consumer Demand and Operations Management Models: A systematic study of Information Technology enabled mechanisms edited by Sergue Netessine and Christopher S. Tang

Authors	Competition	Demand Uncertainty	Single Period/ Multi Period	Strategic Intermediary
Jiang (2007)	No	No	Single	-
Fay and Xie (2008)	No	Yes	Single	-
Shapiro and Shi (2008)	Yes	No	Single	No
Fay (2008)	Yes	No	Single	Yes
Jerath et.al (2008)	Yes	Yes	Multi Period	Yes

Table 1: Taxonomy of Articles on Opaque Products

(Courtesy: Consumer Demand and Operations Management Models: A systematic Study of Information Technology Enabled Mechanisms. Edited by Serguei Netessine and Christopher S. Tang)

3 Variable Opaque Products

The study of variable opaque products(VOP) which is still in its infancy can be used extremely among low-cost airlines where revenue management system has lots of scope for development. VOP are different from opaque products and regular products as they provide customers an opportunity to vary the degree of opaqueness (Post 2010). Blind booking is an

example of this phenomenon as the passengers are unaware of their routes, destinations etc. and the passengers can reduce the opaqueness by deselection of a few characteristics of the product such as flight destinations and can select dates of travel, flight origin etc. Another example of VOP is Sathyam cinemas, Chennai's blind date on Thursday evenings at 7.00 pm

	<u>VOP</u>	<u>Opaque Product</u>	<u>Regular product</u>
<u>Product Characteristics</u>	All Product characteristics not revealed to customer until payment	All Product characteristics not revealed to customer until payment	All Product Characteristics are known to customer
<u>Customer Influence on Opaqueness</u>	Have Influence	No Influence	Not applicable
<u>Refunds</u>	No refunds	No Refunds	Refunds under certain conditions
<u>Examples</u>	Blind Booking at German Wings Blind Date at Sathyam Cinemas, Chennai, India	Hotels at Hotwire, Priceline in USA	Expedia and many others.

Table 2: Comparison of variable opaque, opaque and regular Products

(Courtesy: David Post and Martin Spann)

Figure 1: Blind Booking in Germanwings and Eurowings

Figure 2: Blind Date at Sathyam cinemas, Chennai

where the language as well as title of movie is unknown. Table 2 shows the differences by comparing VOPs, opaque products and regular products. Figure 1 and 2 shows example of blind bookings at German Wings and blind date at sathyam cinemas.

4 Opaque Products Applied in Practice in various Industries

VOP are an extension for industries shown below in Table 3 which have already faced success with opaque products, except for the degree of application of customer's influence. In these industries, methods have been tested out to make products very simple so that it could be easily understood by the customers. Further these industries have made the customers interact to produce suitable price-product combinations.

Industry	VOP	Opaque Products
Airlines, Freight, Cruises		
Hotels, Resorts		
Media, Advertising, Television Network Provider		
High Value Medical Services		
Entertainment, Cinemas, Sporting Events		

Table 3: VOP and Opaque Products in Various Industries

5 Few Useful Propositions

Three useful propositions have been suggested in this paper that would aid all the three parties involved in opaque selling, i.e. seller, intermediary and buyer to be benefitted from the phenomenon.

Proposition 1

The seller holds equal advantage in enhancing his revenues in the same way as the buyer who is appropriately benefitted by purchasing the products/services at lower prices while trading with VOP in industries where there is a low level of horizontal differentiation of the services/products.

Proposition 2

Intermediaries participating in opaque selling will gain substantially in markets where there is an intermediate level of product/service differentiation.

Proposition 3

In an oligopolistic market with a horizontal product differentiation, the firm that sells its regular products at a price lower than that of the opaque products benefits the most among all, considering that all other competitive firms have sold their regular products at a price

higher than those of their opaque products with a greater proportion of their products sold in opaque manner.

6 Concluding Remarks

Selling opaque products produces benefits for service providers as well as for intermediaries. In order to maximize the profit as well as the revenue, service providers should avoid selling on a per unit basis and rather sell in bundles. The first mover always has advantages as one would like his products to be sold by the intermediary. Further, the intermediaries also need to maintain the opacity of the products as well as find and identify appropriate markets and fight aggressively to secure a foothold in the industry. Further, intermediaries need to identify an optimal window size i.e. whether there should be a wide or narrow window of opacity as narrow window though increases the cannibalization of regular products may increase the attractiveness of VOP or opaque products. In future, alternative rationale needs to be developed that would help service provider to offer products for opaque selling which may not have been appropriate and feasible earlier due to either business or technical constraints.

7 References

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